

method⁸. In contrast to the high activity of tributyltin dithiocarbamates⁹ the corresponding dioctyltin derivatives fail to arrest the microbial growth to a significant extent.

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Analytical Applications of Copper(II) in Acetonitrile : Determination of Mercaptans

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COPPER(II) is an excellent oxidant in acetonitrile, possessing high redox potential, suitable stability and the ability to oxidise several compounds¹⁻⁷. Verma and Kumar^{8,9} have recently described the use of copper(II) in acetonitrile for the visual and potentiometric determination of xanthates, organotrithiocarbonates and ascorbic acid in acetonitrile medium. The present communication extends the use of this oxidant to the determination of mercaptans in acetonitrile. The oxidation of mercaptans with hydrated copper(II)

perchlorate in acetonitrile medium is fast in the initial stages but becomes slow as the titration proceeds. The determination can however be accomplished by reacting mercaptans with an excess of reagent in acetonitrile and back-titrating its unreacted excess with standard ascorbic acid in the same solvent using diphenylamine or N, N'-diphenylbenzidine as indicator. The end-point in back-titration may also be detected potentiometrically by using a platinum wire as indicator electrode and modified-calomel or antimony electrode as reference electrode. In visual titrations, the end-point is marked by the sudden disappearance of blue colour. That copper(II) can be smoothly and rapidly titrated with ascorbic acid in acetonitrile medium, has recently been described by Verma and Kumar⁹. The proposed method for the determination of mercaptans is simple, accurate and of wide applications.

Experimental

Acetonitrile: Distilled twice from phosphorus pentoxide (5g/l).

Hydrated copper (II) perchlorate, 0.05N in acetonitrile: Prepared and standardised as described earlier⁹.

Ascorbic acid, 0.05N in acetic acid-acetonitrile: A little more than the calculated amount of the compound was dissolved in minimum quantity of warm acetic acid and the solution was left to attain room temperature, then diluted with acetonitrile to a known volume. The solution was standardised against iodine liberated by the reaction of potassium iodide and potassium iodate.

Mercaptans: n-Butyl, isobutyl, benzyl and dodecyl mercaptans, 2-mercaptoethanol (all Fluka, Switzerland) and thiophenol (Riedel, German) were distilled before use. 2-Mercaptobenzothiazole (Fluka) was used as received.

Indicator solutions: Diphenylamine and N, N'-diphenylbenzidine solutions in acetonitrile, 0.10 and 0.05% respectively.

Procedure: To a known volume (3 to 6 ml) of standard (0.05N) hydrated copper (II) perchlorate were added aliquots of the solutions in acetonitrile of each mercaptan. Each solution was diluted with 30 ml of acetonitrile, kept for 3 to 5 minutes, mixed with 1-2 drops of indicator solution and titrated at room temperature (~23°) with standard (0.05N) ascorbic acid in the same solvent. The end-point was marked by the sudden disappearance of blue colour.

From the volume of standard (0.05N) ascorbic acid used corresponding to the end-point in each titration, the amount of each mercaptan was calculated. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—INDIRECT DETERMINATION OF MERCAPTANS WITH STANDARD (0.05 N) HYDRATED COPPER (II) PERCHLORATE IN ACETONITRILE

Mercaptans	Amount found**†, mg		Amount found***, mg	
2-Mercaptoethanol	4.05	0.026	12.12	0.042
Isobutyl mercaptan	3.96	0.031	12.10	0.042
n-Butyl mercaptan	4.03	0.036	12.10	0.046
Benzyl mercaptan	3.98	0.029	11.87	0.058
Dodecyl mercaptan	4.00	0.041	12.13	0.049
Thiophenol	4.05	0.031	12.02	0.038
2-Mercaptobenzothiazole	3.96	0.042	12.13	0.047

* Amount taken, 4 mg

** Amount taken, 12 mg

† Mean of ten determinations with standard deviation ($\pm$)

Results and Discussion :

The oxidations involving copper(II) as an oxidant in aqueous medium has not gained much importance due to the instability and air-oxidation of the resulting copper(I). The use of copper(II) in acetonitrile has the advantage that copper(I) is stabilised as acetonitrile complex and hence there is little risk of air oxidation. Because of the stabilisation of copper(I) relative to copper(II), the potential copper(II)–(I) couple is increased markedly¹⁰ and this makes copper(II) as a powerful oxidising agent in acetonitrile.

The results indicate that one mole of mercaptan requires one equivalent of copper(II). This corresponds to the oxidation of mercapto group to the disulphide. The overall standard deviation

(Table 1) calculated from the pooled data of all the titrations performed with 4 mg of each mercaptan is 0.034. The same for 12-mg sample is 0.045. It may be mentioned here that the residual copper(II) may be titrated potentiometrically using a bright platinum wire as indicator electrode and modified-calomel or antimony electrode as reference electrode. A sharp drop in potential is observed at the equivalence point in each potentiometric titration.

Because of their importance in biological systems, the determination of mercaptans is of great value. The compounds are quite susceptible to oxidation but much less soluble in water. The application of non-aqueous oxidimetric methods to the determination of mercaptans is therefore of great interest and scope.

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Oxidation of Some Sugars with Ammonium Hexanitratocerate(IV) in Nitric Acid Medium

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VARIOUS oxidimetric methods are available for the determination of sugars¹⁻⁶. In the present work a quick and convenient method has been developed for the milligram determination of some mono and disaccharides. The sugar sample was allowed to react with excess of Ce(IV) reagent at room temperature (25°) and the unreacted Ce(IV) reagent was titrated against Fe(II) using ferroin indicator.

The present method is superior to many other methods in accuracy, quickness and reproducibility. The oxidising reagent is fairly stable and gives clear and sharp end point within the accuracy of $\pm 1\%$.

Experimental

0.15N Ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) solution (A. R., B. D. H.): 20g of ammonium hexanitratocerate (IV) was exactly weighed and dissolved in 8.3 ml of 15 N nitric acid and made up to the mark in a 250 ml flask with distilled water. The solution was standardised by titration with 0.025 N aqueous solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferroin (0.001 M solution) on indicator.

The stock solutions of sugars (AR, BDH) were prepared by dissolving the accurately weighed amount of the sample in distilled water.

Procedure: Aliquots containing 2-10 mg of the sample were introduced in a 100 ml iodine flask and 5 ml of 0.15 N ammonium hexanitratocerate (IV) solution was added to it. The flask was stoppered and the contents shaken well. The reaction mixture was allowed to react for 40 (monosaccharides) to 70 (disaccharides) minutes at room temperature. After